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Spreadsheet Modelling in Fluid Mechanics

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Abstract

Over the last fifteen years, the advent of the spreadsheet in computing has had a huge impact on fields where numerical computations are required, most notably in finance and accounting. However, with the continued development in computational power and graphical capabilities of spreadsheets, new possibilities are opened for their application in the mathematical modelling of physical situations.

This project is an investigation of one such application; the modelling of two-dimensional irrotational flow in fluid mechanics. A simple problem is proposed, that of ideal flow over a cylindrical obstruction, which is analysed and solved theoretically by means of conformal mapping. This analytic solution is modelled using the spreadsheet *Excel V*, the suitability of which is considered and compared to the more conventional use of computer algebra packages.

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1 Nomenclature

$\mathbf{q}$ velocity vector of a fluid particle, $= q_1 \mathbf{i} + q_2 \mathbf{j}$

q scalar speed of a fluid particle, $= \sqrt{q_1^2 + q_2^2}$

ρ density

∇ Nabla operator, $= \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathbf{i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \mathbf{j} \right)$

p pressure

z vorticity

ϕ velocity potential, $= \phi(x,y)$

ψ stream function, $= \psi(x,y)$

a radius of the cylindrical obstruction

2 Introduction

2.1 Mathematics and Fluid Mechanics

Fluid mechanics is the study of fluids, both at rest and in motion with respect to boundaries, where a fluid may be considered a “substance which deforms continuously when subjected to a shear stress”⁽¹⁾. It has a long and colourful history, with its origins dating back to the time of the ancient Greeks, in their attempts to understand and quantify the motion of projectiles through air, and the age-old enigma of flight.

The study is one which historically contains many links with the intricacies of abstract mathematics. These have come about through the attempts to understand and explain empirical results through a rigorous theoretical framework. This was largely initiated by Newton in the second book of his *Philosophiæ Naturalis Principia Mathematica* of 1687, and continued by other famous names in mathematics such as the Bernoulli brothers, Euler and Lagrange.

In the beginning of the 19th century, the important area of mathematical physics known as Potential Theory was proposed by Laplace, which constitutes the theoretical basis behind many areas of physics, including gravitational attraction, electromagnetic theory and fluid mechanics. When applied to fluid mechanics, potential theory has limited use on its own, in that certain constraints have to be placed on the fluid; namely the flow has to be irrotational. Nevertheless, it is a valuable tool, especially in Classical Aerofoil Theory, where one is concerned with predicting flows past variously shaped obstructions.

Since the time of Laplace, there has been many advances in quantifying fluid mechanics mathematically, from the study of viscous fluids by Stokes in the mid 18th century, leading to the Navier-Stokes equations, to contemporary research in chaotic fluid mechanical systems.

2.2 Modelling of Fluid Mechanical Systems

2.2.1 The Requirements of Modelling

The aim of many hydrostatic problems in fluid mechanics is the determination of some unknown variable, such as the lift created by an aerofoil, or the drag coefficient of a vehicle in motion. For such problems, it is beneficial if the flow can be visualised graphically in a manner which gives information on the speed and direction of the flow. This may be done by plotting the *streamlines* of the flow, which are paths that volume elements of the fluid trace over time. Hence the tangent of these lines at any point gives the direction of the flow at that point, while if the velocity field were plotted as a series of vectors, this would provide additional information on the speed of the flow.

In “real life” situations, possibly involving compressible flow around irregular shapes, or a non-uniformity in temperature, it is impractical to determine the streamlines and velocity field analytically; this would involve the tedious task of solving complex partial differential equations. As a result, it is often necessary to resort to numerical techniques, and many industrial software packages have been designed specifically for this. Typically these use the Finite-Difference or Finite-

Element methods involving much repeated calculations, and as a consequence, contemporary fluid mechanics has become very computer orientated.

For any application where numerical techniques are used, especially one as potentially complex as fluid mechanics, a high emphasis lies on optimising algorithms to ensure efficiency of computation, while at the same time maintaining stability and a convergence to the correct solution. As a result, it is beneficial when developing new algorithms to use them to solve a simple problem, whose solution may be determined analytically, and to compare the two solutions.

2.2.2 Use of the Spreadsheet

The aims of this project are twofold. Firstly, to determine and model the streamlines analytically for one such problem with the aid of a spreadsheet, the results of which may be used for the comparison purposes described above, and secondly to assess the suitability of a spreadsheet in tasks such as this.

The latter aim has been attempted as a result of the increasing power of the modern spreadsheet, both in terms of computation and graphical capabilities, and its relative cheapness when compared to software specifically designed for mathematical modelling. Over the last fifteen years since the spreadsheet was first conceived, it has developed into a tool which is well equipped to solve a wide range of problems in many different fields. As a consequence of this, and its ease of use, the spreadsheet has become a very popular device, and further development seems imminent.

Central to the spreadsheet is its two-dimensional architecture of cells which may contain formulae linking one cell to another. This enables it to compute and store a large array of numbers, which could be a direct representation of some physical

quantity varying over two-dimensional space, which could be speed or pressure in fluid mechanics.

These numbers, either calculated from equations derived analytically or using numerical methods, may then be plotted to provide the visualisation of the flow. If the physical quantity is dependent upon boundary conditions or spatial coordinates, the quantity inside the domain may be recalculated after changing any of these values. This is a trivial task in a well-constructed spreadsheet, where the boundary conditions are stored in a few cells, on which depend the many cells which calculate the unknown quantity.

In Chapter 3, a problem in fluid mechanics is proposed, and modelled using a spreadsheet. The resulting spreadsheets are considered in their effectiveness, and compared to more conventional techniques of modelling.

3 The Problem

The problem to be modelled is ideal, irrotational flow past a cylindrical obstruction. The fluid could be liquid or gas, but must be incompressible and inviscid for the model to be valid. Another important constraint is that the flow must only vary over two-dimensions, which could be the (x,y) plane in Cartesian coordinates, as shown in Figure 2.1. Hence the problem becomes one of determining the flow profile over any region of the flow with constant z -coordinate.

Figure 3.1

The problem is somewhat artificial, since no fluid is truly incompressible and inviscid, although there are situations when this is a good approximation, such as some liquids which exhibit very little compressibility, and the behaviour of so-called *superfluids*, a state at very low temperatures at which liquids have zero

viscosity⁽²⁾. However, it is an ideal problem for testing numerical algorithms, as noted in Section 2.2.1.

4 Mathematical Description of the Flow

4.1 Equations Governing the Flow

This chapter derives the equations regarding the two-dimensional ideal fluid-flow of the problem, starting with the general equations of motion, the derivations of which are given in the references listed at the end of the project. These equations form the basis of any modelling techniques, either analytic or numerical.

Let $\mathbf{q} = q_1\mathbf{i} + q_2\mathbf{j}$ be the velocity vector of a volume element of the flow, which has a density ρ . Then the *equation of continuity* may be expressed as:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{q}) = 0 \quad (1)$$

This is analogous to the conservation of mass equation in kinetics and may be derived using the divergence theorem⁽³⁾. The second principal equation incorporates any external force $\mathbf{F}$ acting upon the volume element such as gravity, and the influence of pressure from the neighbouring elements, p :

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{q}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{q} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{q} + \frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p = \mathbf{F} \quad (2)$$

Known as *Euler's Equation of Motion*, this is the result of applying the principals of linear momentum on the volume element described above⁽⁴⁾.

For an ideal fluid, there is no external forces acting, so $\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{0}$, and the fluid is incompressible, so the density, ρ is a positive, non-zero number. Moreover, since the flow is hydrostatic, the velocity vector, $\mathbf{q}$ does not vary with time, so $\frac{\partial \mathbf{q}}{\partial t} = \mathbf{0}$,

and the equations above may be simplified as follows:

Equation (1):

$$\begin{aligned}\nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{q}) &= 0 \\ \nabla \cdot (\rho q_1 \mathbf{i} + \rho q_2 \mathbf{j}) &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(\rho q_1) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(\rho q_2) &= 0 \\ \rho \left(\frac{\partial q_1}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial q_2}{\partial y} \right) &= 0\end{aligned}$$

Since $\rho \neq 0$, this becomes:

$$\frac{\partial q_1}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial q_2}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (3)$$

Equation (2):

$$\begin{aligned}(\mathbf{q} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{q}) + \frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p &= \mathbf{0} \\ \left[(q_1 \mathbf{i} + q_2 \mathbf{j}) \cdot \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathbf{i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \mathbf{j} \right) \right] (q_1 \mathbf{i} + q_2 \mathbf{j}) + \frac{1}{\rho} \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \mathbf{i} + \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} \mathbf{j} \right) &= \mathbf{0} \\ \left[q_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + q_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \right] (q_1 \mathbf{i} + q_2 \mathbf{j}) + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \mathbf{i} + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} \mathbf{j} &= \mathbf{0} \\ q_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (q_1 \mathbf{i} + q_2 \mathbf{j}) + q_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (q_1 \mathbf{i} + q_2 \mathbf{j}) + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \mathbf{i} + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} \mathbf{j} &= \mathbf{0} \\ \left(q_1 \frac{\partial q_1}{\partial x} + q_2 \frac{\partial q_1}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \right) \mathbf{i} + \left(q_1 \frac{\partial q_2}{\partial x} + q_2 \frac{\partial q_2}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} \right) \mathbf{j} &= 0 \mathbf{i} + 0 \mathbf{j} \\ \text{ie. } \left. \begin{aligned} q_1 \frac{\partial q_1}{\partial x} + q_2 \frac{\partial q_1}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} &= 0 \\ q_1 \frac{\partial q_2}{\partial x} + q_2 \frac{\partial q_2}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} &= 0 \end{aligned} \right\} & (4)\end{aligned}$$

The vorticity of the fluid, ζ , which may be thought of as a measure of the "rotation" of the flow, is defined mathematically as:

$$\zeta = \nabla \wedge \mathbf{q}$$

$$= \begin{vmatrix} \mathbf{i} & \mathbf{j} & \mathbf{k} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \\ q_1 & q_2 & q_3 \end{vmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Since $\mathbf{q}$ represents a two-dimensional vector, its partial derivatives in the z -direction are zero, as is its component in this direction, q_3 , and so (5) simplifies as follows:

$$\zeta = -\frac{\partial q_2}{\partial z} \mathbf{i} + \frac{\partial q_1}{\partial z} \mathbf{j} + \left(\frac{\partial q_2}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial q_1}{\partial y} \right) \mathbf{k}$$

$$= \left(\frac{\partial q_2}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial q_1}{\partial y} \right) \mathbf{k}$$

Furthermore, since the flow is irrotational, $\zeta=0$ so:

$$\frac{\partial q_2}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial q_1}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (6)$$

Equations (3) and (6) represent the link between the theoretical basis of elementary fluid mechanics and the powerful mathematical technique of conformal mapping. This is because they are the Cauchy-Riemann equations of the function:

$$f(z) = q_1 - q_2 i$$

In other words, this equation, which is merely the velocity vector with its $\mathbf{j}$ -component negated and represented on the complex plane, is analytic. There are many important results which may be derived from the formulae in this chapter⁽⁵⁾, notably the Bernoulli equation (7), which gives an expression relating the pressure of the fluid to its velocity, density and some constant k . However, the result of

most importance to this project is the derivation of the Cauchy-Riemann equations of $f(z)$.

$$p = k - \frac{1}{2} \rho \mathbf{q}^2 \quad (7)$$

As a consequence of the $f(z)$ being analytic, and from elementary results in vector analysis⁽⁵⁾, it is valid to construct two scalar functions which are the real and imaginary parts of an auxiliary complex function known as the *complex potential* of the flow:

$$w(z) = \phi + i\psi \quad (8)$$

where $z = x+iy$; $\phi = \phi(x,y)$ is the *velocity potential*, and $\psi = \psi(x,y)$ is the *stream function* of the flow. The function $w(z)$ is also analytic, and is related to $\mathbf{q}$ by the two relations:

$$\text{and } \left. \begin{aligned} q_1 &= \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} \\ q_2 &= \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y} = -\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (9)$$

Hence the velocity vector may be expressed in terms of the velocity potential and stream function as:

$$\mathbf{q} = \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} \mathbf{i} + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y} \mathbf{j} = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} \mathbf{i} - \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} \mathbf{j} \quad (10)$$

while the scalar quantity of the fluid speed is given by:

$$q = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y}\right)^2} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x}\right)^2} \quad (11)$$

Upon differentiating (9) and substituting the resulting expressions for the partial derivatives of q_1 and q_2 in (3) and (6), it is clear that the velocity potential and stream function, in addition to being analytic, are both harmonic, i.e. they both satisfy Laplace's equation:

$$\nabla^2\phi = \nabla^2\psi = 0$$

This demonstrates the fact that any problem of the type posed in Chapter 3 could be approached as the finding of a solution to Laplace's equation with a homogeneous Neumann boundary condition at the boundary of the obstruction, since there is no flow in the direction normal to the boundary.

4.2 Visualisation of the Flow

For any two-dimensional fluid flow, there exists a family of streamlines along which the stream function, ψ is constant, and a family of equipotential lines where the velocity potential, ϕ is constant. These lines are always orthogonal to one another, since they always intersect each other at right angles.

Both lines may be used to illustrate the path of the flow, as shown in figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1

4.3 Use of Conformal Mapping: The Zhukhovski Transform

Conformal mapping is a useful mathematical technique often used in fluid mechanical problems. Through its geometrical ability to relate one complex plane to another, a complicated fluid flows may be transformed into a simple flow for the purpose of modelling or solving problems, simply by applying one or more conformal transformation on any formulae describing the flow.

For problems of ideal-fluid flow over an obstacle (any piecewise smooth, connected curve), such as the one in this project, the ultimate aim of conformal mapping is to transform the actual flow into a flow representing a steady, uninterrupted flow. This is done by transforming the obstacle into an obstacle which does not effect the flow, which could be an infinitely thin slit-domain, parallel with the flow. If such a transform can be found[†], then the straight line trajectories of the uninterrupted flow in the codomain of the mapping may be used to predict the obstructed flow in the domain.

[†] It can be shown⁽⁶⁾ that if the flow is sufficiently well-behaved, viz. its velocity at infinity is finite, then such a transform does exist.

In the case of a circular obstruction, such a transform exists, and is known as the Zhukhovski transform:

$$w = z + \frac{a^2}{z} \quad (12)$$

where $w = u + iv$ and $z = x + iy$ are complex variables, and a is a real constant. The plots of the streamlines and lines of equipotential for both the image and its mapping are shown in Figure 3.2, which is generated from the spreadsheet described in Chapter 5.1. This illustrates that the constant a signifies the radius of the obstruction, which maps to the slit-domain on the real axis of the w -plane from $u = -2a$ to $2a$.

(a)
Figure 4.2

The function (12) is not strictly a transformation since both the interior and the exterior of the circle $|z| = a$ maps to the entire w -plane, so no bijection exists between the two planes. This is due to the inverse of the Zhukhovski transform being the quadratic:

$$z^2 - wz + a^2 = 0$$

which gives two values of z for each value of w . A more complete illustration than Figure 4.2(a) is shown below, which additionally shows the trajectories inside the circle, plotted with the aid of the computer algebra system DERIVE. Clearly these trajectories have no physical meaning when the transform is applied to fluid mechanics, since the assumption implicit in the problem is that there is no flow in the interior of the boundary.

Figure 4.3

Since $z = x+iy$, the Zhukhovski transform (12) may be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 w(z) &= x+iy + \frac{a^2(x-iy)}{x^2+y^2} \\
 &= \left(x + \frac{a^2x}{x^2+y^2} \right) + i \left(y - \frac{a^2y}{x^2+y^2} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

When comparing this result with (8), it is clear that the velocity potential and the stream function of the transformed flow in the codomain are as follows:

$$\phi = x + \frac{a^2 x}{x^2 + y^2} \quad (13)$$

$$\psi = y - \frac{a^2 y}{x^2 + y^2} \quad (14)$$

These functions correspond to the horizontal and vertical lines in Figure 4.2(b), which are the constant values of ϕ and ψ in the w - plane. So when set to any constant, they may be solved for y to represent ϕ and ψ in the z - plane, i.e. the velocity potentials and stream functions of the fluid flow around the obstruction.

Using the definitions for vector velocity and speed given in (10) and (11), these quantities may be expressed in terms of the partial derivatives of either ϕ or ψ to give:

$$\mathbf{q} = \left[\frac{a^2(y^2 - x^2)}{(x^2 + y^2)^2} + 1 \right] \mathbf{i} + \left[-\frac{2a^2 xy}{(x^2 + y^2)^2} \right] \mathbf{j} \quad (15)$$

and
$$q = \sqrt{\left[\frac{a^2(y^2 - x^2)}{(x^2 + y^2)^2} + 1 \right]^2 + \left[\frac{2a^2 xy}{(x^2 + y^2)^2} \right]^2} \quad (16)$$

Equation (15) allows one to predict the flow at an arbitrary distance from the obstruction by letting x and y approach infinity. If this is approached along the x -axis in either direction, $y=0$ and so (15) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{q} &= \lim_{|x| \rightarrow \infty} \left\{ -\frac{a^2}{x^2} + 1 \right\} \mathbf{i} \\ &= \mathbf{i} \end{aligned}$$

while if approached along the y-axis, $x=0$ and (15) becomes:

$$\mathbf{q} = \lim_{|y| \rightarrow \infty} \left\{ \frac{a^2}{y^2} + 1 \right\} \mathbf{i} \\ = \mathbf{i}$$

Either way, the flow speed approaches unity in the horizontal direction, from below when approached along the x- axis and from below when along the y- axis, showing that the flow at infinity is unaffected by the obstruction.

Equation (15) additionally provides the theoretical prediction to the locations of the points of maximum and minimum velocity. The former may be found by considering (15) along the y- axis, in which case:

$$\mathbf{q} = \left(\frac{a^2}{y^2} + 1 \right) \mathbf{i}$$

This expression increases in magnitude indefinitely as $|y|$ approaches zero; however the domain of the flow only extends to the boundary of the obstruction, at the points $(0, \pm a)$, where the velocity is $\mathbf{q} = 2\mathbf{i}$. These correspond to the points in Figure 4.2(a) above and below the obstruction, where the streamlines have undergone the maximum "deflection" from their steady-flow trajectories due to the obstruction, and where it would be expected that the speed of the fluid is greatest.

In a similar manner, the locations of the fluid's minimum velocity may be found when considering (15) along the x- axis, whereupon it is apparent that these lie at the points $(\pm a, 0)$, which is the sides of the obstruction adjacent to the direction of

the flow. These are known as the *stagnation points* of the system, and where, according to Bernoulli's equation (7), the pressure is highest.

The above brief analysis of the equations governing the flow, confirms much information that is intuitively obvious about the system, information which is graphically illustrated by the spreadsheets described in the next chapter.

5 The Spreadsheets

This chapter outlines the construction of the three spreadsheets used to model various aspects of the problem. Their aims are to generate graphics illustrating the streamlines, velocity field and speed of the flow. The final result is depicted at the beginning of each section.

5.1 Spreadsheet for the Prediction of Streamlines

Figure 5.1

5.11 Evaluation of Formula

The first stage in modelling the problem is determining an expression for the unknown quantity. When plotting the streamlines, this quantity is found by solving equation (14) in Chapter 4 (page 16) for y :

$$\psi = y - \frac{a^2 y}{x^2 + y^2}$$

$$\text{ie. } y^3 - \psi y^2 + (x^2 - a^2)y - \psi x^2 = 0 \quad (1)$$

In other words, given the radius of the cylinder, a , and the required value for the stream function, an explicit expression for $y(x)$ may be found from the above cubic. This, when plotted, gives the plots of the streamlines, as in Figure 4.2(a). The simplest case is when $\psi = 0$, in which case (1) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} & y^3 + (x^2 - a^2)y = 0 \\ \text{or} & \quad y(x^2 + y^2 - a^2) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

So the streamline corresponding to $\psi = 0$ is along the x -axis, $y = 0$, and the circle $x^2 + y^2 = a^2$, which is the boundary of the obstruction. This does not give any information about the velocity of the fluid along these lines, merely the direction of the flow.

For all other values of ψ , (1) must be solved for y . This may be accomplished by using any computer algebra system. Figure 5.2 shows the solution computed by using *Maple*.

```

11:24 Maple V for Windows - [Untitled] 15.2 Mb; 141.4 Mb
File Edit Format Options Help
> y^3-psi*y^2+(x^2-a^2)*y-psi*x^2=0;
      y^3 - \psi y^2 + (x^2 - a^2)y - \psi x^2 = 0
> solve(%,y);
      %1^{1/3} - %2 + \frac{1}{3}\psi, -\frac{1}{2}\%1^{1/3} + \frac{1}{2}\%2 + \frac{1}{3}\psi + \frac{1}{2}I\sqrt{3}(\%1^{1/3} + \%2),
      -\frac{1}{2}\%1^{1/3} + \frac{1}{2}\%2 + \frac{1}{3}\psi - \frac{1}{2}I\sqrt{3}(\%1^{1/3} + \%2)
      %1 = -\frac{1}{6}(x^2 - a^2)\psi + \frac{1}{2}\psi x^2 + \frac{1}{27}\psi^3
      + \frac{1}{18}\sqrt{4x^6 - 12x^4a^2 + 8x^4\psi^2 + 12x^2a^4 + 20x^2a^2\psi^2 + 4x^2\psi^4 - 4a^6 - a^4\psi^2}\sqrt{3}
      %2 = \frac{\frac{1}{3}x^2 - \frac{1}{3}a^2 - \frac{1}{9}\psi^2}{\%1^{1/3}}
> |

```

Figure 5.2

This demonstrates that there is one real solution to the cubic, and two complex conjugate solutions. Only the first is of interest, since the stream function is defined in the real plane. Thus the required expression for y is given by:

$$y = \%1^{1/3} - \%2 + \frac{1}{3}\psi \quad (2)$$

where %1 and %2 are the expressions given in Figure 5.2. For a given streamline value of ψ , this formula may be entered directly into a spreadsheet, to evaluate y for different values of x . However, problems occur trying to evaluate it for small values of x . This is due to the square rooted term in %1:

$$\%1 = \dots + \frac{1}{18}\sqrt{4x^6 - 12x^4a^2 + 8x^4\psi^2 + 12x^2a^4 + 20x^2a^2\psi^2 + 4x^2\psi^4 - 4a^6 - a^4\psi^2}\sqrt{3}$$

being negative for small x , when the higher order terms in x no longer dominate the expression. This results in a complex component, which, although it cancels out when added to the other terms in (2), has to be manipulated by the spreadsheet. The spreadsheet used in this project, *Excel V* has the capability of

handling complex numbers by the inclusion of special commands in place of complex arithmetic operations. For example, if the result of the addition of two complex numbers w and z were required in a cell, the formula would be:

=IMSUM(w,z)

Although it is somewhat tedious to enter formulae as large as those created using these commands, it only has to be carried out once, due to the ease at which formulae can be copied from one cell to another.

5.12 Structure of the Spreadsheet

The spreadsheet is designed to display eight streamlines around an obstruction of unit radius, ie. $a = 1$, corresponding to eight positive values of ψ at equal intervals. This is an adequate number to give a good representation of the flow. Using equation (2), this generates eight streamlines in the upper half of the plane. As a result of the symmetry of the problem, these may be reflected about the x -axis to produce a set of streamlines in the lower half of the plane.

Each streamline is computed from $x = -2$ to 2 with increments of $x = 0.1$, and displayed on the same graph as an x - y scatter graph, whose coordinates are joined. This is accomplished by means of eight series, each corresponding to constant ψ , the structure of which is illustrated in Figure 5.3. The boundary is represented as a parametrized circle comprising forty coordinates.

SERIES 1						
ψ	x	%1	%2	y_i	y_e	
0.175	-2	1696485375094994321	0.232	-0.232		
0.175	-1.9	1602684724231152471	0.241	-0.241		
0.175	-1.8	533853302116493648	0.251	-0.251		

Figure 5.3

Unfortunately, in *Excel V* there is no easy way to format complex numbers,[†] so the numbers computed for %1 and %2 are shown with the default 13 decimal point accuracy for both real and imaginary component.

The formulae that generates the numbers in Figure 5.3 are listed below in Table 5.1. Once entered, they may be copied down, the only difference in the subsequent rows being in the value for x , which increases by 0.1 in each row.

[†] One way to accomplish this is by the inclusion of the syntax: `=COMPLEX(ROUND(IMREAL(z),n),ROUND(IMAGINARY(z),n))` in the cell, where z is the complex number to be formatted, in this case the formulae for %1 and %2, and n is the number of decimal points to be displayed. This has not been done in this spreadsheet, since it would result in already long formulae more than doubling in size, with the result being merely cosmetic.

Cell reference	Entry
B25	0.175
C25	-2
D25	=IMSUM(-(C25^2-1)*B25/6+B25*C25^2/2+B25^3/27, IMDIV(IMPOWER(12*C25^6-36*C25^4+24*C25^4*B25^2+36*C25^2+60*C25^2*B25^2+12*C25^2*B25^4-12-3*B25^2,0.5),18))
E25	=IMDIV(C25^2/3-1/3-B25^2/9,IMPOWER(D25,1/3))
F25	=IMREAL(IMSUM(IMSUB(IMPOWER(D25,1/3),E25),B25/3))
G25	=-F25
C26	=C25+0.1

Table 5.1

Cells D25 and E25 contain the expressions for %1 and %2 given in Figure 5.2, upon the substitution of the radius size, $a = 1$.

Although the formula (2) should yield a purely real number for y , it turns out that when this is calculated in cell F25, there is a small residual complex component. This may be attributed to computational truncation error, and can be disregarded by including the command =IMREAL() in the formula, which extracts the real component from (2). Cell G25 is simply the negation of F25, giving the streamline in the lower half of the plane.

As a final confirmation that the formula derived in section 5.11 gives the correct streamlines, the coordinates of each streamline, computed in the eight series, are redefined in the complex plane and are mapped using the Zhukhovski transform. These are then plotted in a graph similar to Figure 5.1, representing the w -plane, which is shown in the screen capture of the whole spreadsheet, see Appendix A.1.

This demonstrates that the streamlines are indeed straight lines, parallel to the x-axis. The mapping takes place in a second set of series, as shown in Figure 5.4. Again, the formulae generating these numbers are shown in Table 5.2.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
69									
70		x	y ₁	z ₁	w ₁	Re(w ₁)	Im(w ₁)	Im(w ₂)	
71				=x+iy ₁	=z ₁ +1/z ₁				
72		-2	0.232	-2+0.23230107+0.174		-2.49334	0.175	-0.175	
73		-1.9	0.241	-1.9+0.240266+0.174		-2.41801	0.175	-0.175	
74		-1.8	0.251	-1.8+0.250699563203		-2.34496	0.175	-0.175	
75		-1.7	0.264	-1.7+0.2645332569004		-2.27435	0.175	-0.175	
76		-1.6	0.282	-1.6+0.2811258393995		-2.20620	0.175	-0.175	

Figure 5.4

Cell reference	Entry
B72	=C25
C72	=F25
D72	=COMPLEX(B72,C72)
E72	=IMSUM(D72,IMDIV(1,D72))
F72	=IMREAL(E72)
G72	=IMAGINARY(E72)
H72	=G72

Table 5.2

The coordinates in the z- plane to be transformed are given in cells B72 and C72, which contain a direct reference to the results of the first set of series. These are expressed as a complex number in D72 and transformed in E72. Cells F72 and

G72 extract the real and imaginary component, so that they may be plotted in the normal way.

In addition to the eight streamlines in the upper and lower half of the plane, the coordinates of the circle, also representing the streamline $\psi = 0$ is mapped, giving the slit-domain described in Section 4.3

5.2 Spreadsheet Representing Velocity Field

Figure 5.5

This spreadsheet is a modification of a spreadsheet designed to display the gradient fields from differential equations, outlined in a book about using mathematics with *Excel*.⁽⁷⁾

5.21 Evaluation of Formula

For any given vector field $\mathbf{v}$ in some domain, where

$$\mathbf{v} = f(x,y)\mathbf{i} + g(x,y)\mathbf{j},$$

a plot of the field can be constructed by evaluating $\mathbf{v}$ at equally spaced points over the domain. At each point $P(x_0, y_0)$, the vector may be plotted by determining two coordinates either side of P , as shown in Figure 5.6

Figure 5.6

The numbers required for these coordinates are given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
 x_1 &= \left[x_0 - \frac{a}{2} f(x_0, y_0) \right] & \text{and} & & x_2 &= \left[x_0 + \frac{a}{2} f(x_0, y_0) \right] \\
 y_1 &= \left[y_0 - \frac{a}{2} g(x_0, y_0) \right] & & & y_2 &= \left[y_0 + \frac{a}{2} g(x_0, y_0) \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

where a is a weighting constant, if a reduction or increase in the size of the vectors is required to aid presentation.

5.22 Structure of the Spreadsheet

The easiest way to evaluate a large number of such vectors needed for a vector field using a spreadsheet is by the construction of a large grid, as shown in Figure 5.7. By using a partitioned grid where two rows are used for each value of x_0 and two columns for y_0 , an intersection of four cells is available to compute the four required coordinates. A grid large enough to compute 121 vectors was created for this spreadsheet, resulting in an 11x11 set of vectors

Figure 5.7

The functions $f(x,y)$ and $g(x,y)$ are given by equation (15) in Chapter 4 (page 16). Since these functions are used many times in the spreadsheet, it is beneficial to create them as a user-defined function in a macro. This is easily accomplished using the following syntax:

```
Function my_f(x As Single, y As Single) As Single
    my_f = (y ^ 2 - x ^ 2) / (x ^ 2 + y ^ 2) ^ 2 + 1
End Function
```

```
Function my_g(x As Single, y As Single) As Single
    my_g = -2 * x * y / (x ^ 2 + y ^ 2) ^ 2
End Function
```

Both formulae contains the unassigned variables x and y , rather than the conventional cell references used in a spreadsheet to denote a variable. If the complete x - and y - coordinate ranges shown in Figure 5.7 are assigned the variables x and y , the user-defined formulae above may be directly entered

anywhere in the grid, in which case the variables x and y assume the unique values of the four-cell intersection. The formula in all 121 four-cell intersections are shown in Table 5.3.

Coordinate to be calculated	Entry
x_2	=IF($x^2+y^2>1,x+0.5*a*my_f(x,y),0$)
y_2	=IF($x^2+y^2>1,y+0.5*a*my_g(x,y),0$)
x_1	=IF($x^2+y^2>1,x-0.5*a*my_f(x,y),0$)
y_1	=IF($x^2+y^2>1,y-0.5*a*my_g(x,y),0$)

Table 5.3

It was noted in Section 4.3, page 15, that the predicted flow velocity from the Zhukhovski transform has no physical meaning inside the boundary of the obstruction, so in each of the four formulae above there is a test of whether the coordinate (x_0,y_0) lies outside the boundary, $x^2 + y^2 = 1$, using an =IF() command. If the test is true, the coordinates of the vector is calculated, otherwise all coordinates at that point are equated to zero, and as a result, no vector is plotted at the coordinate.

Once (x_1,y_1) and (x_2,y_2) are computed for all vectors over the desired range, the individual coordinates may be plotted as a set of individual data-series in an x-y scatter graph, with the required pairs of coordinates comprising the vectors joined by lines.

5.23 Discussion and Implementation

The range over which the vectors are plotted may be entered by the user, by defining the minimum and maximum values of x and y , upon which the increment between the vectors is calculated and the x - and y - coordinate ranges updated. In this manner, it is easy to “zoom in” to any region of interest in the domain, simply by changing the range and altering the scale of the graph. The range illustrated in Figure 5.5 and the screen capture of the spreadsheet in Appendix A.2 is of the upper right-hand quadrant.

This clearly illustrates that the longest vector, and hence greatest velocity, lies just above the obstruction, as would be expected with the uninterrupted flow traversing horizontally. The shortest vector, signifying the lowest velocity, lies near the extreme right of the obstruction in the vicinity of one of the two stagnation points at either side of the obstruction, as noted in Section 4.3 (page 18).

5.3 Spreadsheet Representing Speed

Figure 5.8 Surface plot representing the fluid's speed around one quarter of the obstruction.

5.31 Structure of the Spreadsheet

In terms of structure, this spreadsheet is similar to the one described above to represent the velocity of the system. The speed at some point of the domain is a scalar function of the (x_0, y_0) coordinate of that point, given by equation (16) in Section 4.3 (page 16). This may be entered in a grid akin to the one illustrated in Figure 5.7, with only one cell at each $x_0 - y_0$ intersection, all containing the formula shown in Table 5.4.

Variable to be calculated	Entry
q	=IF(x^2+y^2>1,SQRT(((y^2- x^2)/(x^2+y^2)^2+1)^2 +(2*x*y/(x^2+y^2)^2)^2),0)

Table 5.4

The same test, as to whether the point lies outside the boundary is carried out as before, and the speed taken to equal zero if the test is false. Once a number of these cells is evaluated over some range, they may be plotted directly as a 3d surface plot., rendered two-dimensional as shown in Figure 5.8 by adjusting the elevation of the plot until it is viewed from above.

5.32 Discussion and Implementation

A 30 x 30 grid representing 900 calculations of speed over the domain was used to create the plot in Figure 5.8, where the domain is the upper right-hand quadrant as in the previous spreadsheet.

This grid resolution is sufficient to give a good profile of the variation of speed over this domain, while being reasonably quick to calculate. Running on a 486-DX33 computer, the time necessary to compute the speeds was of the order of half a second, while the time necessary to plot the results is much greater; approximately 5 seconds.

As with the velocity spreadsheet, the range over which the speeds are calculated may be entered by the user. The results in Figure 5.8 confirm the fact suggested by the velocity field plot and predicted theoretically on page 17, that the lowest

velocity lies either side of the boundary, and the highest on top, where the fluid races over the boundary.

Perhaps what is not so obvious is the paths of the region boundaries, indicating equal values of speed. Figure 5.8 shows that these paths circulate around the obstruction, with the exception of the middle path. This represents the boundary between the magnitude of the flow being above and below unity, and projects in an almost linear fashion from the obstruction.

6 Conclusion

It was noted in the introduction that the principle aim of this project has been to assess the effectiveness of spreadsheets in fluid modelling. However, since the problem posed in Chapter 3 is of a potential flow type, the findings would be just as relevant to the other applications of potential theory.

In fluid mechanics, potential flow is very idealised, but has many important applications, including the generation of aerofoils using conformal mapping, and the prediction of the air flow around them. This is also, in essence a flow around an obstruction problem, and may be tackled in much the same way as the problem in Chapter 3 - by finding a suitable conformal mapping and considering the transformations of the streamlines by the mapping. Problems such as these merely involve the manipulation and plotting of complex numbers, and are therefore ideal for spreadsheets using the techniques discussed in this project.

Unfortunately, for more realistic flow problems in fluid mechanics, ie. when the fluid is non-ideal, perhaps with measurable viscosity and compressibility, spreadsheets of this type are of limited use, since the degree of mathematical complexity is much greater in these cases, and there may exist no analytically-based technique for determining the variable to be modelled. Nevertheless, such problems can often be modelled by solving the equations governing the system numerically, which often means a discretization of the flow domain into a regular mesh of equally spaced nodes and elements, and so may be representable in the form of spreadsheet grid. However, the suitability of using a spreadsheet over specifically written software would be dependent on the nature of the calculations.

For example, if the technique for computing the solution varied from one spatial point to another, no unique formula would exist for every cell of the spreadsheet

grid, unlike the case of the spreadsheet modelling the speed in this project. A simple example of this is in the case of viscous flow over an obstruction, where there exists a *boundary layer*, as shown in Figure 6.1. This is the region adjacent to the obstruction when the velocity of the fluid rapidly varies from zero at the obstruction to the velocity of the mainstream. Any numerical method at determining the flow in this region would differ from the region of mainstream flow, and a spreadsheet would have to identify in which region the point represented by each cell lies. This could be achieved by logically analysing the coordinates within each cell and using a set of macros to calculate the flow, depending in which region the cell was found to be.

Figure 6.1

However, the use of macros in this way shifts the emphasis away from the cell structure of the spreadsheet to the external code, thus calling into question any advantages the spreadsheet has over high-level languages such as FORTRAN or C.

There are many numerical techniques within the field of computation fluid dynamics, which unlike the above, do not vary over space. These include schemes which are concerned with modelling non-hydrostatic flow problems, ie. systems

which vary over times, as in the case of diffusion and advection. In these problems, each step of the computation represents the change of some quantity over a time interval. Calculations of this nature may easily be carried out on a spreadsheet as a series of single iterations over the whole region of interest, where each iteration signifies an advance in time. Such problems typically involve no higher computation requirements than that of the spreadsheets described in this project, and so represent another potential application of spreadsheets.

For the many types of problems which demand more complex computations, the current mathematical limitations of spreadsheets do impose restrictions on their successful application. As an example, the handling of complex numbers by *Excel V* is far from ideal, as demonstrated by the long formulae required in the first spreadsheet, listed in Chapter 5.12 (pages 24 and 25). In this spreadsheet, even the relatively simple Zhukhovski transform generated long and unwieldy strings of syntax, which when copied to many cells occupies large amounts of memory. Also, only the most basic mathematical functions are pre-defined, especially for the evaluation of complex variables, and these must be used to define more complicated functions by the user. These deficiencies, and others which may make computer algebra packages and specifically written programs currently more suitable for the evaluation and manipulation of numbers, may easily be addressed in future versions of spreadsheets, if sufficient demand warrants it.

In this chapter, some of the restrictions imposed on problems have been outlined in order for them to be successfully modelled using a spreadsheet. Although the class of problems is somewhat limited, this project has sought to illustrate the fact that the spreadsheet does have a potential, and as yet largely untapped use in fluid mechanics, and in the many other areas of mathematical physics where the two-dimensional modelling of some quantity is required, being an accessible and easy-to-use, yet powerful and diverse piece of software.

7 References

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- (5) JEFFREY, Alan "Complex Analysis and Applications" CRC, 1992
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- (6) KAPLAN, Wilfred "Advanced Calculus" 4th ed. Addison Wesley, 1991
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In addition to the above, the following sources have been useful for background reading:

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ACHESON, D J "Elementary Fluid Dynamics" OUP 1990

Appendix A Screen Captures of the Spreadsheets

11:03 Microsoft Excel - STRM_LNS.XLS 17.1 Mb; 139.9 Mb

File Edit View Insert Format Tools Data Window Help

A40

Streamline Predictions for Flow Over a Cylinder

8 data series.

Stream function, ψ from: 0.175
 to: 1.5
 => increment 0.18563

w-plane

z-plane

SERIES 1				SERIES 2			
ψ	x	%1	%2	ψ	x	%1	%2
0.175	-2	169648537509499432	0.232	0.340625	-2	8916656	
0.175	-1.9	160268474231152471	0.241	0.340625	-1.9	9422202	
0.175	-1.8	533853302116493648	0.251	0.340625	-1.8	5486073	

Sheet1 Sheet2 Sheet3 Sheet4 Sheet5 Sheet6 Sheet7 Sheet8

17:51 Microsoft Excel - VELOCITY.XLS 16.2 Mb; 139.2 Mb

File Edit View Insert Format Tools Data Window Help

Representation of Velocity Field

x from:	0
x to:	2
=> x increment:	0.2
y from:	0
y to:	2
=> y increment:	0.2
Vector weight:	0.12

	0	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8
0	0	0	0	0	0
0.2	0	0	0	0	0
0.4	0	0	0	0	0
0.6	0	0	0	0	0
0.8	0	0	0	0	0
1	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0	0

Ready

Appendix B A Comparison between Spreadsheets and Computer Algebra Packages in Modelling the Speed

As an attempt to draw some comparisons between the efficiency of modelling the problem of the type outlined in Chapter 3 using the spreadsheet *Excel V*, and the more conventional use of computer algebra packages, the results of the third spreadsheet, which models the speed, was recreated using the popular computer algebra packages *Mathematica 2.2.3* and *Maple V release 2*. This spreadsheet, which perhaps is the most computationally demanding of the three, was modified to model the speed at twice the resolution of that described in Chapter 5.3, by doubling the size of the grid and so performing 3,600 calculations of speed.

The results are illustrated on the following pages (B.1, B.2 and B.3). In each plot, the contours which separate the regions of varying speed are clearly visible, and there is a good agreement in their positioning. The times taken to generate these plots in each case are as follows, when running the software on a 486DX-33 computer with 8 Mb of memory, under Windows:

Mathematica	42 seconds
Maple	10 seconds
Excel	11 seconds

Table B.1

Before drawing any conclusions from the above data, one has to consider the amount of computation time devoted to the calculation of the data, and the time spent generating the plot, which may be considered independent to the complexity of the problem. In the case of *Excel*, the time devoted to calculation was only of the order of half a second, the remainder of the time spent updating the plot. This is in contrast to the performance of *Mathematica*, where most of the time was

The above image was created in *Mathematica* upon execution of the following commands:

```
In[1] := f:=If[x^2+y^2>1,Sqrt[(2 x y/(x^2+y^2)^2)^2+((y^2-x^2)/(x^2+y^2)^2+1)^2],0]
```

```
In[2] := ContourPlot[f,{x,0,2},{y,0,2},PlotPoints->60,Contours->{0,0.2,0.4,0.6,0.8,1,1.2,1.4,1.6,1.8,2}]
```


The same result (above) was created in *Maple* by the following commands:

```
>f:=proc(x,y)
  if x^2+y^2>1 then
    sqrt((2*x*y/(x^2+y^2)^2)^2+((y^2-x^2)/(x^2+y^2)^2+1)^2)
  else 0 fi; end;
>with(plots):
>contourplot(f,0..2,0..2,numpoints=3600, axes=BOXED);
```


A 60x60 grid created in Excel V, with each cell containing the formula:

$$=IF(x^2+y^2>1,SQRT(((y^2-x^2)/(x^2+y^2+1))^2+(2*x*y/(x^2+y^2+1))^2),0)$$

resulted in the above image when plotted as a 3d surface plot. This spreadsheet is saved as spd3600.xls on the disk included with this project.